

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL THOUGHT IN AZERBAIJAN

Aslanova G.

Department of Pedagogy, Ganja State University., Azerbaijan Gandja city

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Abstract

The purpose of the course "History of School and Pedagogical Thought in Azerbaijan" is to teach students and future teachers the gradual formation and development of the history of school and pedagogical thought of the Azerbaijani people. The role of national traditions and national thinking should be specially noted here. The history of school and pedagogical ideas in Azerbaijan is ancient and rich.

Keywords: Pedagogical, history, national, specially, students.

Introduction. Even before the emergence of pedagogy, which is the science of teaching and upbringing, folk pedagogy was used in the education of the young generation.

Folk pedagogy is the content, purpose, means, methods, organization, etc. of education. It is a collection of pedagogical knowledge, experience, views, rules and traditions that the laboring masses have acquired as a result of daily observations throughout history, gathered under the influence of living conditions. This pedagogy is based on folk philosophy.

The scope of folk pedagogy is very wide. There are many valuable ideas in folk pedagogy about the role of health, mind, knowledge of enlightenment, beauty and hard work in the development of a person as a perfect personality, in terms of new modern pedagogical concepts, physical, mental and aesthetic education, moral and labor education.

Folk pedagogy has been serving the spiritual purity and beauty of the people for years and giving them aesthetic pleasure.

People say: "You must be beautiful and perfect"; "A man's outwardly elegant inner self should be gentle." Therefore, the unity of natural-physical beauty and intellectual-spiritual perfection is considered necessary for true beauty. However, as it is said in the "Koroglu" saga; "It is very rare for a person to be both outwardly beautiful and smart and perfect." Although many of them are not very handsome in appearance, they are polite in behavior and attitude, rich in intellect, brave and noble in character. Among the people who look beautiful on the outside, there are also those who are ugly on the inside.

In the materials of folk pedagogy, intelligence is considered a prerequisite for the beauty of meaning, and the following signs are often mentioned. The people who value intelligence highly say: "Strength breaks everything, intelligence breaks strength", "The head is the crown of the body", "A person is known by the head", "In this world, a smart head is better than wealth and money, a black stone is better than a skull that does not understand", "Intelligent the head can profit from everything" and so on. That's why the proverb teaches: "When you grow tall, grow your mind", "When you grow a camel's neck, grow your mind like a hoof" and so on. "What is needed to grow the mind? Knowledge,

science". It is not for nothing that it is said that "Science is the lamp of the mind". "Science is obtained not by sleeping or money, but by working."

There are many valuable ideas in folk pedagogy about ways and means of acquiring knowledge and knowledge. Acquaintance with them shows that in the work of intellectual education, hardworking people mostly use the methods of storytelling and explaining, interviewing, visualizing, as well as riddles, epics, proverbs, problems, songs, etc. they used a lot of tools. There are also issues of family upbringing, age periods of the child, the expediency of starting education at what age, etc. we also find very valuable ideas about

It is possible to select them not only from the examples of oral folk literature, but also from the epics that were considered the epitome of education in the Middle Ages, in which "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" is of exceptional importance.

"Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" is one of the oldest examples of Azerbaijani literature, one of the ancient pearls of Azerbaijani folk pedagogy.

This epic written about 1300 years ago is a centuries-old cultural monument of our people. This saga, which consists of a prologue and 12 stanzas, resonates with the events taking place in medieval Azerbaijan. This saga, rich in examples of heroism and patriotism of our people, has been spreading from mouth to mouth for 1300 years, spreading from hand to hand, from village to village, calling children and young people to fight for the Motherland.

In 1999, the 1300th anniversary of the "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" saga was widely celebrated both in our republic and in a number of foreign countries.

The events held in foreign countries, including jubilee events in Dresden, Germany, at the residence of UNESCO in Paris, celebrating the jubilee of "Kitabi-Dade Gorgud" in the Turkish states, as well as in Iran, Georgia, Russia and other countries, show the global importance of Dade Gorgud. Holding a summit meeting of Turkish states in Baku, developing and implementing a long-term program in the field of "Kitabi-Dade Gorgud" promotion and dissemination, creating a special Dade Gorgud scientific research laboratory, filming serial films, etc. shows the breadth of the scale of such events.

The holding of extracurricular lessons and competitions on the epic in all secondary schools of the republic, scientific conferences and seminars in higher schools, the preparation of publications for children on the theme of "Kitabi-Dade Gorgud" in various languages, and the scientific-pedagogical, spiritual and educational "Kitabi-Dade Gorgud" emphasizes the importance

The celebration of the 1300th anniversary of Grandfather Gorgud became a great holiday of our people, including the history of pedagogical ideas. Our people are proud of having a monument of words in our written and oral literature that can compete with the most magnificent epics of the world. "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" tells about the antiquity of folk pedagogy. "Kitabi-Dade Gorgud", which is older than "Manas", "Sasunlu Davud", "Epic about Igor's regiment" or "Koroglu", is an ancient and rich pedagogical monument of Turkic-speaking peoples.

"Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" is the holy book of the Azerbaijani people. This book is told from the mouth of a holy person - Deda Gorgud, the spiritual father of the Oghuz tribe. Dede Gorgud was a complete connoisseur of oguz. He could have said anything, he would have given all sorts of news. The truth would inspire his heart. The inspiration given by the Almighty to the hearts is a revelation. Revelation is given to prophets. From the saga, it seems that Deda Gorgud was the prophet of the Oguz tribe until the time of Prophet Muhammad.

"Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" is an eternal cognitive book that embodies real-life events according to its content. In the stories included in this book, judgments are given that are always necessary about people's spirituality, outlook, today and tomorrow. Dede Gorgud, with his wisdom, intelligence, scientific guide, comes alive in the imagination as a person who is the embodiment of great, enlightened, mind and understanding.

It clearly proves that "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" is a bright page in the history of pedagogical ideas of the Azerbaijani people and that educational ideas in the epic are of great importance. These ideas and motifs are used in our epics created after "Dade Gorgud" ("Koroglu", "Shah Ismayil", "Ashiq Garib", "Asli va Karam", "Tahir va Zohra", "Gurbani", "Ashiq Valeh", etc.), as well as to a number of prominent artists, from Nizami Ganjavi to Samad Vurgun, gave artistic and pedagogical food to one degree or another.

In general, oral folk literature of Azerbaijan is a rich area of our artistic and pedagogical heritage. Oral folk literature has an educational character in its essence. For example, Azerbaijani proverbs and proverbs

emerged historically as a wise result of the people's experience of morals, cultural behavior and household rules, in the process of their social labor activities and mutual relations. Azerbaijani oral folk literature can be evaluated as an encyclopedic pedagogical resource due to its pedagogical content. Lovers occupy a prominent place among the creators of this literature.

In the 17th century, Abbas Tufarganlı, Sari Ashik, Ishta Gasim and others in the 18th century were among them. Folklore examples created during these times say that the world ruled by feudal slavery is a dark house, "that evil world, many cry, few laugh", there "the judge does not make a sofa, there is not enough crying", "the enemy does not allow a person to smile", "he can't remember his friends, because his hands are empty, his face is black", "a person's dignity is measured not by his mind, but by his wealth", "if you are smart, they will laugh if you are poor". In order to oppose that world and eliminate injustice, people must unite. Because "unity is life", where there is unity, it is possible to move a mountain. From various genres of oral folk literature, including "Koroglu", "Abbas and Gulgaz", "Khaste Gasim" and others. it is possible to bring examples from epics.

Those ideas, which formed a certain page in the history of pedagogy, still retain their power of educative influence, instilled in the national-ethnic memory of the young generation. , is educating in the spirit of respect for the spiritual wealth filtered from the people's thinking.

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